

Biocuration: from Evidence to Classification

Episode 2 Transcript and Show Notes

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Episode 7 Transcript

Alex Nguyen Ba: The sequencing of the human genome was seen as the largest international and collaborative effort in biological sciences, costing about \$3 billion. Starting in 1990, it took 13 years to reach what was a very good draft, and the sequence was considered fully complete only in 2022. There are zero bases left to determine, except, of course, the variants that make us who we are. To this end, as of today, millions of humans have had their genomes sequenced. But more important than sequencing genomes is mapping the effects of variants in those genomes. And having an atlas of variant effect is one of the holy grail achievements in the field of genetics. You might ask yourself, why are scientists doing this? Well, each of us have a unique set of DNA variants that make us who we are. But as we learned in previous episodes, some of these variants can cause disease.

The field of clinical genetics is currently focused on cataloging all variants that are known to be causal for many different diseases. But how is this done? Is there something like a Wikipedia page where scientists can just go and enter their experimental results and some expert later reviews the edits? And if so, how do they deal with the millions of variants that are being uncovered every day from these large sequencing efforts? And what are some of the challenges regarding privacy, ethics, and the interface with clinicians. Today, we dive into the field of bio-curation. Just like a museum curator, bio-curators manage the collective human knowledge about biological entities. And you can imagine this is not easy when it comes to DNA variants, and the job is made even more complicated due to the nature of clinical assessments.

And now with the advent of multiplex assays of variant effects, bio-curators must integrate large-scale experimental data to variant interpretation, a path that is not always straightforward. This has made it even more challenging with the rise of computational predictors that were introduced in the previous episode. How are they being used alongside MAVES? To help us think through these questions, we reached out to two experts that are going to teach us about bio-curation and the challenges of building an archive of variants.

[Intro music plays]

Welcome back to the VUS podcast, a series initiated by the outreach efforts of the Atlas of Variant Effect Alliance. I'm Alex, a professor at the University of Toronto, and today the team, Evelina, Adrine, Moez, Kortni and I will walk you through the challenges surrounding bio-curation and the maintenance of clinical variant classification. In the field of human genetics, everything is rare, and so describing their effects need to be done with caution. Today, our two hosts, Moez and Evelina, we'll guide you through the conceptualization and interpretation of variants for usage by clinicians. We'll discover how scientists all over the world share data and how to understand which variants are benign versus pathogenic. As always, we would like to note that this podcast focuses on a realistic portrayal of the basic and translational research behind rare diseases with the hope that it will lead to better patient care. But this podcast is not meant to be medical advice.

Evelina: Hi, I'm Evelina.

Moez: And I'm Moez. Today, we will take a look at the behind the scenes of clinical variant classification and their respective databases.

Evelina: First, we need to understand the utility of these databases when it comes to clinicians giving diagnoses. When a clinical geneticist receives the result of a genetic test, what do they have access to? As you can imagine, it's probably not a simple report like when you take a test on 23andMe. Presumably they have something more than just a simple lookup table that says whether you're more likely to have a certain mutation or not.

Moez: Is this data backed by large, multiplexed experimental studies? Were computational predictors integrated in the analysis? We learned in previous episodes that MAVE assays don't always test for disease phenotype directly. So how can the clinician use this data?

Evelina: So today we'll look at two fundamental challenges regarding the field of "biocuration". The first is to simply collect and manage all the scientific knowledge we have on disease genes. This can be the collection of variants that have been observed, or the experimental effects of each variant. The ultimate goal of biocuration in this field is to establish whether variation in a specific gene can cause disease, whether there are actions we can take to improve clinical outcomes given a genetic risk, and to establish which variants cause disease or if they're neutral. That means that biocuration is deeply intertwined with variant interpretation.

Moez: And the second major important issue is the synthesis of different lines of evidence to understand if a given genetic variant is benign, aka: harmless, or pathogenic, aka: harmful, and to understand how we collate all this data into databases of information to form some giant database to aggregate all the sequencing and experimental data from the functional genomics field. When dealing with personal data, you can imagine the privacy and ethical considerations of this work.

Evelina: In this episode, we welcome two authorities in this field that can explain to us some of the challenges in better detail. First, we welcome Dr. Courtney Thaxton, who leads curation teams for ClinGen, a massive resource for clinical geneticists. Thank you, Dr. Thaxton, for joining us today. Can you please begin by introducing yourself?

Courtney Thaxton: Yes, my name is Courtney Thaxton and I am the assistant professor at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill in the Department of Genetics. I also happen to be the director of the UNC Bio-Curation and Coordination Core that is part of the Clinical Genome Resource.

Evelina: Can you let us know how you got involved with genetics and transitioned from functional assays into clinical genetics?

Courtney Thaxton: Well, absolutely. So I studied at the University of Central Florida, and cell biology. So everything started with me with signal transductions. And as I went through my PhD and postdoc, definitely a lot more molecular information came in. I started studying about Neurofibromatosis type 2, right? Which is a genetic disorder caused by variation in the NF2 gene. And then moved on to look at more myelination. But at some point in my postdoctoral years, I ended up being funded by a patient advocacy group called the Pitt Hopkins Foundation. And I remember going to a conference with them and this conference was very unique because the patients and the parents were there. And that was really a moment that struck me. Not only

was I looking at the people who raised the money to pay for the work that I was doing, which was very model organism- focused, but I was realizing that one of the issues coming up over and over again was it took two years, five years, 10 years, 20 years to get a diagnosis. A child was misdiagnosed because this disease has very similarities. So that's where I think my shift and my work went from being very bench science, where I did do a lot of experimental functional assays coming into clinical genetics. I just wanted to see what I could do to help narrow and reduce that gap in time where someone was getting a diagnosis that leads to the treatment, it leads to the support, it leads to the answers that you can start to build and really understanding the trajectory of life for a person with a genetic disorder, but also their family and their support system around them.

Evelina: It is so moving to know that experts become motivated to serve and ease the pain of families, especially ones affected by the diagnostic odyssey.

Moez: Dr. Heidi Rehm is another expert passionate about genetic testing and has a unique perspective on the framework for clinical genetic testing. Dr. Rehm, can you begin by introducing yourself and telling us a little bit about how you got involved with clinical genetic testing?

Heidi Rehm: I'm Heidi Rehm, and I work at both Mass General Hospital and the Broad Institute. I've always had a fascination of human biology and particularly genetics. Never knew what to do with it until I started working in the lab in college and enjoyed lab work. So pursued a PhD in genetics at Harvard University and during that time, I was doing research on genetic basis of hearing loss, there's hundreds of genes that lead to isolated hearing loss, and so that really started my fascination with the field of medical genetics and rare disease genetics. And then after my PhD, I started a postdoc in David Corey's lab in the neurobiology department. But within a couple of years of being in David's lab, the opportunity to build a new clinical lab as part of what was then called the Harvard Partners Center for Genetics and Genomics arose. And I took the leap to start building a brand new clinical lab as part of that effort. And so I started hiring people and launching clinical tests.

Moez: One of the points we always bring to these conversations is about the barriers for getting genetic testing. Can you talk about what is the workflow for a patient to receive a genetic report?

Heidi Rehm: Sure, so patients come into different places to get genetic testing. Traditionally, they'd go to be referred at some point to the medical genetics clinic because someone appreciates that they may have a genetic disorder. Increasingly, they're now going to subspecialties based on the organ impacted, whether it's cardiovascular disease, neurology, know, renal, etc. And so there's a lot of specialty clinics that also support genetic testing. And then we're even now launching a lot of programs in preventive genomics in primary care, working with primary care patients, recognizing that a lot of patients don't actually get the referrals they need and get the testing they need. So any one of those venues, a patient might show up and get a genetic test, which then might lead to either a negative, a positive, or an inconclusive result. Obviously, their journey next varies depending on which of those outcomes they have.

You know, if it's positive and a cause is identified or a genetic risk is identified, then they'd be cared for based on that result. If it's the dreaded variant of uncertain significance, then sometimes

things are pursued to try to clarify that, other times they're not. And there's a lot of work we're doing to help sort of guide those next steps.

Evelina: Dr. Rehm is talking about variant interpretation, something Dr. Thaxton is very familiar with, as she worked on this from an experimental approach and then from a bio-curation lens. Dr. Thaxton, in the functional genomics field, there are a lot of subclasses of work, like variant interpretation, functional assays, bio-curation, MAVEs, and sometimes even we get confused. Can you please define bio-curation for us?

Courtney Thaxton: Absolutely. There's probably a lot of different definitions we can have. Quite literally, it means the collection of biological data to curate that. And certainly when we think about it for variant interpretation, it's being able to extract important elements about a person, the variations, their gene, and their phenotypes from literature, from data we're collecting as clinical records, and be able to put that together in a framework. And hopefully resources we can assess downstream for variant pathogenicity.

Evelina: And what resources are available today for biocurators to help them with variant interpretation? Do these large-scale multiplex assays help you?

Courtney Thaxton: Well, the great thing about these types of functional assays that are produced in large amounts is the fact that you have the ability to hopefully test multiple variants. And that's really important for clinicians and, you know, variant scientists, diagnosticians, anyone who's looking at doing that kind of assessment of pathogenicity or benignity. These functional data actually helped to support that there's consistency of whatever the abnormality is that variant is having. So, MAVE data can be really important in that aspect to bring in that functional data element. They're also important in some ways, whether it's a large scale MAVE or just a functional assay in general, to understand the mechanism of disease.

Evelina: I think one of the things that people outside the curation field don't really know about is how much research you have to do for any specific disease gene. The association of gene and disease, the population and the data, the phenotypes. Back then, it was probably many isolated papers, but now hopefully, MAVE can consolidate all of this.

Courtney Thaxton: At this point, you know, as a biocurator myself, I have to look at so many different resources to collect all of this data, right? As we mentioned, biocuration means to collect. So I can collect that from primary literature. I can collect that from databases. And so MAVE is great that it has these databases, but I think it will be really important as we go into the future where MAVE can be integrated, right? Into resources like ClinVar, where you know clinicians are going there quite frequently to look at variant interpretations.

Being able to have those connections to the resources clinicians are using a lot is going to be really important. But is there even thought that this information is included in electronic health records? If we think about the first touch point where a clinician's getting information back post testing a patient, it's going to be in that health record, reducing the time that an individual, any individual has to chase, look, or find that particular data is wonderful. I think now with MaveDB though, consolidating one area where everyone can submit and collect all this information is

already such a fantastic resource coming from me as a biocurator. It's a top line place I can go hopefully and look for that information and look for my gene before I go anywhere else to search for additional data.

Evelina: And talking about the variant interpretation, we know that there are barriers like education of providers, financial barriers to maintain and publish research and access to databases, as well as the consistency to keep track of changes and different versions of the data. Can you tell us more about how you see the integration of all of these moving parts into biocuration?

Courtney Thaxton: Absolutely. I mean, functional assays are coming a long way, right, from how we perform them. I think what is a nice thing to do, and hopefully this podcast and just all the work that we're doing in general, in ClinGen and other places, will just begin to educate individuals of how their information is used by a downstream user, being able to provide not only access to that data, but understanding the data. This is something as a biocurator that's difficult in general, just from published papers, we respect that there are word limits from journals, right? And that a lot of times important information is left out. So the same for when we think about functional assays and MAVE data, it's gonna be really great as it continues to grow that more people not only are submitting and including MAVEs, but that there's some kind of consistency, right, of terminology and approach in how you present that data. And making that very clear to the downstream user, thinking again, as a clinician, they're gonna need to know things less about maybe the full statistics, but just knowing is the result abnormal versus is it normal? Right, something very straightforward. I think it's just a perception for us to think about more broadly.

Evelina: There any other issues that come with depositing data for these sorts of experiments? For example, Alex's lab has a ton of MAVE and variant-specific data that is just sitting around, waiting for the paper to get written and published. But there are some challenges with funding and the overall scientific ecosystem to get this data out there.

Courtney Thaxton: I think other hiccups are just to data sharing in general. We need to have more data sharing, more people engaging in it. And that's certainly increasing, but we have to respect that with data sharing, depending on the type of data being shared and also the location of that person, their politics within their institution, their country and others. That is a little bit of a hurdle. I think we're all trying to move past, but we can't leave the elephant in the room not noticed, right? We have to talk about this. So I really think that as more and more people can begin to share their work across whether it's journals or having databases and resources where if they don't have the funds, the money or ability to publish to a paper, can they still submit this data for someone to use? I think another barrier in general, just thinking about in the future, because this is how my brain always goes, is sustainability. How can we make sure that we can sustain these types of resources? So even if that individual that submitted that data is no longer able to submit it, that their data stays for us to access it.

Evelina: Going back into biocuration for a second. For museums, you have experts in specific historical times or geographic areas that are doing the curation. You can go and learn about these areas in school or through research in these communities. But how can this happen with biology? Do you have to be an expert in some disease? Or do you have to be an expert in just a single gene?

Courtney Thaxton: So a GCEP is a gene curation expert panel. This is a panel within the clinical genome resource or ClinGen that is focused on looking at whether a gene has a relationship with the disease. So it's definitely one of the great things that these groups get to do is look at different genes that may be included on genetic testing panels for certain clinical areas or diseases. We can think hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, hearing loss, retinal dystrophy, lots of different disorders. And so they'll look at these genes, where these assertions have been made and really use our framework that ClinGen has developed to understand, yes, there is a definitive relationship between this gene and disease, or no, this is disputed. There's evidence for and against, and we're not sure, or completely refuting it. There's so much extra evidence to say this is absolutely not involved. That becomes really important because it helps to get out some of that extraneous information.

Evelina: So the expert panel has to decide which gene is involved in some disease? How do you reach that standard? At which point can we look at the experimental evidence and make a definite conclusion?

Courtney Thaxton: It's with all due respect to science and the history, but we all know that as technologies improve, we discover more new information every year. So what we thought 20 years ago about something has changed yesterday. And so this is how that framework is supposed to say. Let's set some guidelines and consistency for figuring out those genes and their involvement with disease.

Evelina: One of the problems with genes is that they are sometimes involved in many traits. Is biocuration only focused on the one gene - one disease association?

Courtney Thaxton: The other thing I love about the GCEPs in particular and the task they get to do is defining that disease entity. So really they do have to look at those 30 % of genes that are involved with more than one phenotype and really begin to understand for the curation, whether or not those assertions, are they accurate? Do we see if a gene's associated with four phenotypes? Are they all distinct? Are some of them, are any of them part of phenotypic spectrum, which we know can happen? The great thing is we have so much genetics to help back it up. What we used to do by a physical appearance of features. We can now go, well, while one looked more severe than the other, they both have the same variant underlying it. This is a spectrum. We have to respect the way that people present with their phenotypes, their severity is all also influenced by not only their other genes that they have, but their environment, their food, the exposures they have. And so this is where using this framework really gets into that area.

Evelina: As you know, MAVES are supposed to help annotate variants. Usually scientists do this for known Mendelian disease genes to discover unknown variants. Can you walk us through how gene curation leads to efficient variant curation?

Courtney Thaxton: We do have a goal in ClinGen to curate all genes associated with monogenic disorders. So we're looking at those 5,000 plus genes and continuing to curate. Now, once a gene curation expert panel or that GCEP has found those definitive and strong gene disease relationships. That allows our VCEPs or a variant curation expert panel to now move on to their task. And their task is really to help adapt those current American College of Medical Genetics

and Genomics or the ACMG variant interpretation guidelines. And while ACMG came out with these guidelines and they've been really useful to help create that framework, we know that some of them need to be adapted to specific phenotypes. And that's exactly what these ClinGen variant curation expert panels do.

Evelina: In a previous episode, Dr. Debbie Marks made the comment that MAVEs, although useful for variant interpretation, are only as good as the assay that they were done in, and that different MAVEs on the same protein but looking at different properties can give different answers. Is this something that these expert panels encounter frequently during the variant curation process?

Courtney Thaxton: Their work is to look at conflicting interpretations of variants within the resource ClinVar. This whole process is FDA recognized. So it tells you the rigor with which we do this variant curation and forming these expert panels. But that also means that is helpful to have that stamp of three-star status and FDA recognized when clinicians and users are going to ClinVar, especially for those conflicting interpretations. This is what helps to, again, helpfully resolve those conflicts.

Evelina: And what do you do with variants of uncertain significance?

Courtney Thaxton: We will always have the issue of the VUS and then I think that's where we loop back around to the importance of MAVEs and functional assays. Being able to have those well-established assays, have the right controls with them, which include known benign and pathogenic variants can really help us to move out of the increasing number of variants of uncertain significance or VUS and really getting to move them to one of the more terminal classifications we consider pathogenic and benign.

Evelina: So you emphasize here the importance of having clear, well-established assays that can have strong concordance between variants and the disease phenotype. This doesn't always exist, right? And sometimes an assay can improve over time. So do you have to be constantly on the lookout for better assays for the same gene? What is the guideline?

Courtney Thaxton: It's a very good question. We do have guidance to ask groups to come back every two to three years to update their specifications. In fact, ClinGen is participating in the next version four of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics with AMP and CAPS variant interpretation guidelines. We do have those implementations coming into play. The great thing is, is that as assays become available, a VCEP can decide at any point to update our specifications. ClinGen has already published some guidance about what we consider a well-validated functional assay from Bernick et al. in 2019. So I think that helps set the stage for us and for all of our VCEPs. They look at this guidance when they're determining what can meet a strong criteria for functional assay versus moderate or supporting, or you can't use it at all.

Courtney Thaxton: I think anyone still performing an assay should perform that assay, right? Publish that work, get it reviewed and get it out there. It can at least start the conversation and hopefully lead to more work being done.

Evelina: So right now you might be working with a couple of different assays for the same gene. You'd have to look for new assays that might support or contradict one another. Is that right?

Courtney Thaxton: We expect that this may have to evolve with time, especially as technologies get better. Who knows where the assays get so well validated. You don't need 11, right? You may be able to reduce and still see a same odds of path ratio that could get you from supporting to a moderate or even a strong strength.

Moez: And odds of pathogenicity ratio is a statistical measure that takes into account the number of pathogenic variants in a gene, the prior, and the expected assay score for these variants.

Courtney Thaxton: I think the nice thing is, is that as the guidance itself, for variant interpretation is changing and moving to a more semi-quantitative metric, that will also be a pro in thinking about updates to this. We're not going to have these moderate, strong, supporting. We're going to have positive and negative points. That allows range in between those, which I think is really nice.

Evelina: So really this whole exercise is a sort of variant centric view of disease. Would you say that's correct?

Courtney Thaxton: No one's arguing this person that a clinician diagnosed by their phenotype and phenotypic features has this disease. What we are questioning is the variant that you are calling out here, is that the responsible variant? Because there could be more. All of us have millions of variants. We could have missed something. It could be non-coding. Was the genotyping method done really well? Did the bioinformatics of the sequencing drop a variant, you know, for whatever reason? Those are the things we have to think about in the back of our head as variant scientists. And so those are the questions we will ask.

Evelina: Obviously, if the assay is not well validated in the direction of causality, then it makes the whole process more complicated. Now you have a lot of different variants that may or may not be involved in disease and you only have more information to decipher.

Courtney Thaxton: So certainly I think having those well validated assays helps our VCEPs work and our groups will look for these at the heart of everything we're doing is trying to get patients the best results and the results for their health. Having VUS is not that area, right? That's not only an unknown significance, that's an unknown trajectory for that individual for potential clinical trials and certain treatment methods. So certainly I hope more people read these papers and just think about validating their assay.

Evelina: In a previous episode, we learned that there were currently a few thousand disease genes known to be strongly associated with a named disease. But because rare diseases are rare by definition, we'll likely find more over time. Does that make the world of biocuration harder? Would you not eventually need 20,000 expert panels for every gene in the human genome?

Courtney Thaxton: I don't know that's a good question. Right now in my head, I'm like, I need to go to OMIM and see if I can pull out what has been the average gene discovery, right? Of new

genes added to OMIM over the last few years or any of our literature. Certainly in doing some of the curation, we can see that papers and journals like the American Journal of Human Genetics have a whole section. Here's new gene disease, validity associations. And I think this happened on the order of every time those journals are published, right? Once a month. The key is that's an assertion. What's the data to back it up?

Evelina: Once a month, that must mean that data is streaming in at a record pace.

Moez: Actually, you might not know this, but a very large challenge in computing is the streaming of biological data sets. Some of you listeners might remember a time when data transfers were slow. And even saving data into a hard drive might've been painful. Sequencers these days produce gigabytes of data every few minutes, and sequencing projects employ many of these sequencers simultaneously. Having solved this though, someone now has to do something with the data. And that's the flip side to the challenge of biocuration, data collection and sharing. In this field of rare disease, every instance counts. And so we need to understand how scientists deal with all the thousands of terabytes that are produced daily. To get at this, we went back to Dr. Heidi Rehm at the Broad Institute who generously explained to us how data is collated for variant interpretation.

Heidi Rehm: Quickly, as you're doing high throughput sequencing, you realize the biggest bottleneck is the interpretation of the variation. And so over time, I realized that there's gotta be a better way to do this as a community instead of each clinical lab working in isolation. And that was the early stages of really thinking about what is now ClinGen.

Evelina: ClinGen is the clinical genome resource and is involved in the aggregation of genomic and health data.

Heidi Rehm: Krista Martin and David Ledbetter had organized the cytogenetics community to share information about gene deletions and duplications and the probes being used in arrays for cytogenomic microarrays and kind of had a community organized on the cyto side. So then we decided to put in a grant to really organize the community on the sequence variant side.

Moez: So working on the sequence variant side, are you basically trying to predict a person's causative variant for a known disease? Or are you just looking at specific variants and asking if it can cause disease in some individuals?

Heidi Rehm: Actually, there's a little bit of nuance to it. One is the classification of the variant with respect to pathogenicity. And the other is the genetic interpretation of an individual based on an indication for testing and their phenotype or genetic risk interest. So in terms of variant classification, that is the step where you aggregate all of the evidence about a variant and you classify it with respect to a given condition. And so you may say this variant is pathogenic for cystic fibrosis in an autosomal recessive manner. And that is arguing that it is capable of causing disease.

Now I use the word capable because just because someone harbors a pathogenic variant doesn't mean they have or will develop disease, which is based on A, inheritance pattern. If it's recessive,

you need something going on in the other allele. B, the penetrance. We use other terms to qualify that as well as which organ systems may be affected, like the expressivity. So pathogenic, you know, is in that context of can cause disease. When we say benign, we're saying it doesn't cause disease, although we try to clarify that with respect to, again, the condition, it is benign for cystic fibrosis. Now, later on, someone may associate it to a common disease, in which case that's a separate question. So those terms really need to be contextualized with the question you're answering, which should systematically start with those diseases for which that gene has a valid role.

Moez: Right, because presumably not only do variants have contexts in which they become pathogenic, but also variants do impact protein function in some form, and it's probably not always clear what that might do.

Heidi Rehm: Hence, a lot of our work in defining gene disease validity is the first step. On the other side, if I have a patient with an indication like cystic fibrosis, then I run a genomic analysis. I'm interpreting their genome, looking at variation, and looking for any pathogenic variation that might explain their symptoms. And I may find pathogenic variation, there's nothing to do with their symptoms, and say negative, oh, but by the way, they're a carrier for this variant, or they have this risk, or I may say positive, they have a pathogenic variant that I believe explains their indication for testing. how we think about those terms.

Moez: And so what about conflicting variants?

Heidi Rehm: So conflicting basically means that two different groups judge the pathogenicity differently. And so that could be what we sometimes call medically significant differences where one lab will say it's pathogenic or likely pathogenic for something and another lab will say it's either uncertain, likely benign or benign because those big differences often will lead to differences in how you manage that patient. And so we consider them medically significant. And you can also be conflicting because one lab says it's a VUS and another lab says it's benign. That's also conflicting. But often that wouldn't be as likely to influence changes in care management. So they're kind of a different category in terms of importance of working on them.

Moez: Okay. So how do we classify a variant? Dr. Thaxton earlier spoke about odds of pathogenicity that tries to take into account all possible forms of evidence to classify a variant?

Heidi Rehm: Yeah, so the main ways that groups classify variants, I can say for one, is was it in a peer-reviewed publication? And somehow magically, if it was in a peer-reviewed publication as disease-causing with some random term, that was considered evidence of pathogenicity. And which of course, as we all know, wasn't a good measure. Also, there was a tendency to assume that if a variant was absent from the population, often assessed by looking at least a hundred controls, that that was also evidence of pathogenicity. So those were in some ways the primary ways. Now those publications might've involved a functional assay. Of course, that can be coincidental as we all know, the absence from the population, we all know now that that's really, and certainly not 100 people, does that give any statistical significance. But that was a lot of how it was being done. Could you reference a publication where a researcher said it was, you know,

found it in a patient with disease, and could you show that it was absent from the general population?

Moez: For things like rare diseases or novel variants, this strategy doesn't make that much sense. So this was how it was done a long time ago. How is this done now? Was there an update on the procedure for varying interpretation?

Heidi Rehm: Right. So we really tried to say no longer is it the case that just because it's published that it is there for sufficient evidence for pathogenicity. And instead you really needed to look at the elements of evidence to judge that. And the references were simply ways of finding the evidence out and about. And so we went through and we really tried to define all the types of evidence that you might gather and generate and then use professional opinion in a lot of ways to say, how strong is that evidence? We did mention that even though we might be assigning a particular default strength of evidence that you could modify that strength by adding on PM3 supporting to say, normally this is moderate, but we're going to call it supporting for this application. So we had a method to modify the strength, although I will say that it was somewhat biased in defaulting to the inherent strength that was coded, which is one of the limitations, I think, of the guidance today. But we're trying to define the evidence and give them sort of a way to think about combining disparate pieces of evidence together to arrive at an overall classification.

Moez: So this is really a framework. to standardize the way scientists think about classifying a variant. But surely some folks might have objections on the specific strength applied to certain evidence. In a past episode, we talked about AI and variant predictors. Not everybody wants to use them for every case.

Heidi Rehm: We definitely continue to see variation in how people apply those rules. What we find is when we get groups together to discuss the evidence and the rationale for applying different codes, we ultimately almost always agree with each other in the end, with some rare exception. But it's not uncommon that we disagree at the start. And it really shows you that there is complexity there and that we have to continue evolving the objective aspects of varying classification and not have to rely as heavily on subjective aspects. And one thing that's been nice is that a lot of companies and groups have tried to automate the application of the ACMG guidelines, and that is the direction we need to head. The challenges, the ones that are most automatable tend to be the least quality evidence ones. Unfortunately, I've also seen misapplication and misclassification because they're relying on the things that are automatable and not the more valid types of evidence and they're double counting things.

That said, I think we're moving to an era where we're actually starting to share and critically think about the underlying evidence and structure that data, whether it be standardizing the phenotypes of individuals with HPO terms and OMOP as a data model for using All of Us, UK Biobank, really starting to standardize phenotype, standardizing functional assays as you guys are working on with MAVE.

Moez: So after all this work, you've now built a resource that people can just look up the expert opinion on a variant. Is that right? Can you tell us how this came to be?

Heidi Rehm: Yeah. So there are a couple of precursors. So before the NCBI, a colleague of mine, Patrick Williams, had the idea that they would create a database infrastructure and that groups would submit their classifications to it and share it from many different sources. And now there wasn't a funding model for this. And so the funding model was tied to, okay, if you're submitting to it, then you can use it for free. But if you're not submitting to it, then you pay a licensing fee to access it. And they were going to try to create some framework of getting labs to submit, but then trying to come up with a funding model that would sustain it. So a number of us, myself, Sherry Bell, others were working with Patrick knowing that we needed a solution. And so while we were kind of trying to develop this project, but had our inherent concerns about the model, we discovered NCBI was interested about developing some sort of database because they had the dbSNP database and they were trying to tie different resources together. This would be a better place to have this database. And so they were interested, we were interested, and by working together, we guided NCBI in terms of what the clinical community and research community needed. And they built that database at NCBI. And then that removed this sort of conflict. And then on the ClinGen side, my grant, which involved David Ledbetter, Bob Nussbaum, Krista Martin, and myself, we funded about eight or nine labs with money to help them have the resources to figure out how to share their data in ClinVar.

Moez: Since ClinVar aggregates mostly variants from patients, there's an inherent prior of finding more pathogenic variants. Does this ever affect people's perspective when they look at just population sequencing data? I think you have also worked on aggregating data from these massive sequencing projects.

Heidi Rehm: Yeah, and in fact, that is certainly an observation. Just the sheer massive increase in volume of data in gnomAD has led to more times when people are like, oh, there's a pathogenic variant here, why there shouldn't be. This is a control population to which I respond, no, it's not the control population. It's the general population. And there are data from biobanks. Also, when you recruit for a common disease, you're not actually necessarily screened to eliminate the likelihood you have other things going on like hearing loss or vision loss when you're being recruited for a schizophrenia or a cardiac disease complex thing, so the database does have a lot going on. The UK Biobank is a general population data set, we'll be incorporating the All of Us cohort. There are people with rare diseases. So there is definitely pathogenic variation.

Moez: Right. So now it's really more about this implicit idea that pathogenic variants have to be rare in the general population because of natural selection. Doesn't that have issues as well?

Heidi Rehm: We published a paper looking at variants that look pathogenic and asking how often are they actually pathogenic like predicted loss of function variants. And you see that a huge percentage of these are actually rescued in some way. Either they're in minor transcripts or they're downstream of the nonsense immediately decay site or they're rescued because of an alternate cryptic splice site or there's all sorts of ways that things that look pathogenic may not actually be. But that whole part aside of misassessment of pathogenicity, there are still true pathogenic variants in gnomAD.

They're either later onset lower penetrance or they are people actually with disease. Everything is there. And ultimately we really just need to connect the phenotype to all the aggregate data we're

generating so that when you find your variant in gnomAD, you can actually look up the phenotype of that individual and get medical records and all of that, which you can do in the UK Biobank, in the All of Us cohort. So as we switch to focusing on biobanks consented for phenotype sharing, that will really help us in these types of analyses.

Moez: And these databases and the MAVE data that are being produced now are likely to be used for biocuration purposes. And of course, who knows which new data set will be produced in the future. We asked Dr. Thaxton to comment on whether this is becoming unwieldy or whether there's some natural evolution to some new database.

Courtney Thaxton: That's a really interesting question. And I think it may be one of those things where we're going to see an evolution of all of those options, right? It might be right now that there could be individual databases or places where there are annotations to functional data. It's a hot topic, but it would be nice though if somehow, just like we have gnomAD as a resource, those started off as several separate independent resources and it went from exAC to gnomAD. So it evolved with time as it got more data. And so that could be something too, where you have MaveDB and others, it's a resource there. It's there for everyone. And that might be the central repository that happens and annotation occurs.

Evelina: Back to Dr. Rehm, one of the problems with phenotype sharing is that people might not truly know the extent of the genetic effects. This is a big issue with pleiotropic genes. Dr. Rehm has an interesting story about this.

Heidi Rehm: There are genes associated with both vision loss and hearing loss. And if you only test their vision but you don't test their hearing, well, you haven't assessed whether that gene could be implicated in their hearing. A great example in my PhD was studying a disease called Norrie disease, which everybody knew involved congenital blindness, and later onset hearing loss. But no one appreciated that there was an underlying vascular component. And it wasn't until we studied this large kindred in Costa Rica that happened to be living in rural conditions and they didn't wear shoes most of the time. And there was added environmental impact to the lower limbs. We discovered that there was a significant peripheral vascular disease component.

It added trauma to their lower limbs from the kind of environment of farming and various things that made this a little more prominent than most of the other families. But then we started surveying all of the families about vascular phenotypes. Turns out 75 % of them had it. It was an X-linked disorder. It's only in men. Turns out they all have erectile dysfunction. But I can tell you no ophthalmologist or audiologist ask that question when they come to get their hearing tested or their vision tested. But it turns out, the entire phenotype is based on a vascular malformation and lack of effective development that underlies everything. And of course that also causes peripheral vascular disease, erectile dysfunction, and a variety of other things. But like that's just an example. You don't know if you don't ask the question.

Courtney Thaxton: I think the most interesting part is the fact we have to understand what's the disease entity. I say that because we have over 5,000 genes associated with disease per online Mendelian inheritance, 30 % of those are associated with more than one disease entity, one phenotype. So while functional assays are really awesome, for those 30 % of genes, there is going

to be more than one phenotype associated. And that doesn't mean that the one assay you have is great for those all variants. So I think some of the work that has to go into MAVEs is just understanding what is the mechanism that you're testing here and how that relates to a potential gene disease relationship. And as a curator and within ClinGen, that's what we take very seriously into consideration. You can start to look at interpretation and classification of variants, but if you don't understand the gene disease relationship overall, then you can start giving out a lot of confusing and conflicting interpretations for a variant.

Moez: And to make sure that the research evidence is accessible as widely as possible, the matchmaker exchange system was developed, right?

Heidi Rehm: Yeah. So today, most of the use of matchmaker exchange is bringing two researcher clinical groups together who have both identified a variant in what's considered a candidate gene for disease. And you're looking to find other cases that can help build your evidence story. However, we also connect a few other sources of information and linkages to other people. That includes ModelMatcher, which links researchers interested in different specific genes or diseases with individuals who've got candidates in those genes. That helps link candidates identified by clinical research with basic science researchers doing work in those areas.

Moez: How can scientists balance sharing data for clinical classification with publishing requirements? Is the matchmaker exchange system used for data that was not publicly shared yet?

Heidi Rehm: So that is a good question. I think largely we've used these matching systems when the data is not publicly shareable. And the case of the matchmaker exchange, which is focused on gene matching, the real issue we found when we first met with all the groups, we were like, how can we share all this data and improve the discovery of the genes implicated in rare disease? The biggest issue is that nobody wanted to publicly share their candidate gene. I'm gonna get a publication out of this, it's a novelty discovery. I just need a couple more cases and I'll get them at some point

Evelina: Lot of scientists sit on unpublished data for years due to the process of publication. And people suffering from rare diseases already have to wait a very long time to get an answer. How can we lessen the competitiveness of publications so that data can reach patients faster?

Heidi Rehm: In the era of the common rare diseases, where one investigator over time could amass enough, we're now at the tail end. Most of the genes we have yet to discover are fewer than one in a million. No single researcher, clinical lab, clinician will ever see more than one case with a particular, varying a particular gene. And so it was this dilemma of, you think you're going to build enough evidence, but you're not. Like we need a new system. But it was getting them over the data sharing barrier in a way that allowed data sharing, but only when it was going to be productive with someone who had the same evidence you had. So you were on equal footing and you're both like identified to each other at the same time.

Nobody's finding somebody else's data without their knowledge. And that was just a real way to get over that anxiety barrier of data sharing. And then the other thing is patient privacy. So the variant level matching concept is really because we just can't put genomes out on the internet and

protect people's privacy. So we have to think about innovative ways to query and access that data when we can't actually put it out there. And that's why we have to construct these sort of federated networks.

Evelina: What about the privacy of MAVE data? Do we need a special location for the clinical use of large data sets?

Heidi Rehm: In my mind, functional data is something that doesn't need to be protected. There's no patient privacy issues for the most part. And so we should put it everywhere it needs to be. And the more we can bring it all together, the better. So I think figuring out where MAVE data should sit so that everybody knows it's there. And that's why I was advocating to bring it into ClinVar in some way, because that's where everybody goes to find out about a variant today. But ideally, you'd actually not just be going to ClinVar, but you'd go to some system that's helping you assimilate data and actually classify the variant.

And so that system would be pulling in MAVE data in ways that it's appropriate to apply that evidence in classification, not just showing it to you. Right? So you could think about ways to bring it in, in ways that help use it as opposed to just show it. That's where I think the evolution needs to happen.

Moiez: One of the things that our podcast focuses on are these Multiplexed Assays of Variant effects (MAVEs). And of course, the use of known clinical variants are super useful for calibrating MAVs. Where do you see the future of MAVEs in this sphere of data aggregation? Are we going to just stockpile MAVEs for many, many genes?

Heidi Rehm: Probably the investment in systematic introducing mutations across a gene will usually be after you've implicated it in at least one disease. And then you start to sort of dissect out its role in that, and potentially others. I mean, there's certainly genes for which one region, when disrupted, leads to one phenotype, a different region disrupted leads to a different phenotype. And so there are genes that have immense complexity in terms of the phenotypes they lead to, and so dissecting that out will absolutely require MAVEs and different MAVEs in a lot of ways.

Moiez: Most of our discussion today has been centered around specific disease gene relationships and their variants. But we probably don't even know all of the single gene Mendelian diseases. And as we added pleiotropic genes, this seems like it might be difficult to sustain all these resources. Where are we in terms of identifying disease genes? Do you think this is the database or will it massively expand in this new era of human genetics?

Heidi Rehm: We are still a ways away. I mean, if you look at the data from Mike Bamshad, Jessica Chong, Debbie Nickerson, it was published where they looked at two variables. One was gene constraint and gnomAD, where you say, well, if this gene is constrained, let's say for loss of function variation, then you could argue that those are probably disease genes. Likewise, they looked at animal models where those genes lead to phenotypes in animals. And so if you take both of those data sets together, saying you have one or the other, you're talking about 10,000 more genes, if you require both to be true, constraint, and there's an animal model, that estimates about

5,000 more genes to be discovered. So something along that range, and we've only discovered about a little under 5,000 today. So my guess is we're halfway there in terms of rare disease gene discovery.

Moez: But what about rare disease genes that have multiple phenotypes or different penetrance? It can potentially increase the complexity of applying functional data for classifications.

Heidi Rehm: Well, it's a great question in the sense of... one of the work groups we have in ClinGen is called the lumping and splitting work groups, my favorite work group name. But one question is how you define a disease. And we've spent a lot of time in ClinGen defining diseases and when to lump and split. And let me just give you an example of that. It goes back to my roots in hearing loss. So there's a gene, *SLC26A4*, and it was associated with two conditions, isolated hearing loss, called *DFNB4* hearing loss, and Pendred syndrome. Pendred syndrome involves hearing loss and thyroid disease. So these were two separate conditions associated to this gene.

However, when we looked at the variation, and families, we discovered A, families with the same variants, some can have pendred and some have isolated hearing loss. B, the mutations that were underlying each were not distinct. They were all loss of function variants in essence. So ultimately we said, all right, this is not two distinct conditions. It's all Pendred syndrome. It's just that the goiter associated is not a fully penetrant phenotypic feature. And so only a small fraction actually develop the thyroid disease. So there in the end, I can say this gene is associated with one condition. That condition has two phenotypic features. The hearing loss is highly penetrant. The goiter is very low penetrance. So now let's move on to something more complex, Marfan syndrome. Everybody knows that *FBNI* is associated with Marfan syndrome but no one's ever called it 18 different diseases. They just recognize that Marfan syndrome has like a whole bunch of different phenotypic features.

Evelina: Marfan syndrome is a genetic disorder that affects connective tissues. Because connective tissues are all over the body, there are more than 30 signs and symptoms that are related to the bones, eyes, the cardiovascular system, the lungs, and more.

Heidi Rehm: And each patient has some but not all of them. So, it comes down to like all this complexity and what you're really wanting to ask about is how many different distinct pathogenic mechanisms can we identify per gene that lead to distinct conditions associated with those distinct pathogenic mechanisms? Or like in this case of *GJB2* hearing loss, there's three different pathogenic mechanisms. There's loss of function, leads to recessive hearing loss. There's gain of function variants that not only disrupt the protein itself, but disrupt the wild type copy, aka gain of function, which can lead to dominant hearing loss. And then there's syndrome-like hearing loss involves skin disease.

Why? Because they're gain of function mutations that not only disrupt the wild type copy of *GJB2*, but also disrupt other homologous gap junctions and disrupt the ones that function in the skin. So you've got one gene that over time you figure out three pathogenic mechanisms, two gain of function but with even different paths of how they operate and one loss of function leading to three different diseases and associated. How much diversity in these things there will be out there? Honestly, I can't even guess because every time I study a gene, the complexity gets worse or

deeper. So I don't know off the top of my head, on average, every gene is probably involved in at least two conditions. Now there's some that is only one, but there are some that it's like 15 already. So somewhere in that range.

Moez: Given how complex genetics can be, do you think there is ever a point or a good time to just step back and potentially redefine what we mean by having solved a genetic disease and all its causative variants?

Heidi Rehm: We are actually doing that right now, as you may know from the Gregor Consortium, and trying to define, solve, some of it is just the terminology we all use, because we all use different ways to say solved, or that was a diagnostic variant, or it's probably solved, or possibly solved, or likely solved, or it is the same evolution we went through in variant classification of the terms pathogenic, probably pathogenic, possibly pathogenic mutation. So we're working on that and we're also working on trying to define what's the evidence level to then use that term in terms of the pathogenicity of variants you find, in terms of the gene disease validity and phenotype matching. Also, what if I have a patient with three phenotypic features and I find that their hearing loss is due to *GJB2*? But that's only explaining their hearing loss, but they have two other phenotypic features. What do I say? Is that solved or is that not? So we would call that a partial solve because we've solved part of their phenotype, but not all of their phenotype. So these are terms that we're working on developing formal definitions, both terminology wise, as well as the actual evidence levels.

Moez: Will our definition of solved involve some form of scale for penetrance? Maybe because we all know there's environmental factors that also influence disease expression.

Heidi Rehm: Yeah, so absolutely. And one of the reasons I differentiated the term pathogenic as can cause disease, but doesn't mean it will cause disease, is because of all of the factors of penetrance and variable expressivity that will govern what actually develops in an individual. But you're absolutely right that over time, we will figure out what are the modifying factors, be they genetic, environmental, various things, and try to paint a picture. And already, work is being done in that space. There's been data published to show that the penetrance of breast cancer in individuals with *BRCA1* or 2 variant relates to polygenic risk scores that modify the likelihood of development of disease.

And so there are now labs that are giving back not only their *BRCA1* and 2 variants, but also with a polygenic risk score and combination to help put them on a more distinct path of the likelihood of developing breast cancer or whatever disease may be of concern. So I think over time, we will get more sophisticated. We will understand more of those factors. Like there's forms of hearing loss that require two variants, and you get no phenotype without one, and you get the phenotype with the other. So those are very concrete factors versus the example I gave with breast cancer. It's a mild modifier, but isn't like, if I have this polygenic risk score, I will get breast cancer if I don't, you know, like it's not that concrete.

Moez: The more complex a disease is, the less obvious it is to diagnose based on their genomes, right?

Heidi Rehm: I think the biggest challenge I have is the more oligogenic disorders like autism where we know genes for which certain types of variation are implicated in autism. The statistical data is clear. But if I have a patient with autism and I analyze their genome and I find a single loss of function variant in a gene that has absolutely been implicated in autism, it's hard for me to say that variant has caused their phenotype and is the sole cause of their phenotype. Both of those questions are very hard to answer when you're talking about oligogenic disorder and where there may be major contributors. It's possible that that one variant I just found actually has nothing to do with their autism and they got their autism due to three other factors. And the next patient, that one variant, the same variant could be the cause of that other patient.

Moez: Thanks a lot for your time, Dr. Rehm. I think you've given me lots to think about when it comes to the future of precision medicine and why variant classification and interpretation is really the center of it all.

Alex Nguyen Ba: Thank you, Dr. Thaxton and Dr. Rehm for joining us today. In this episode, we saw how clinical data is really complicated and it really needs expert to curate and for variant interpretation. With big data, the challenges in clinical research are slowly shifting from a technology barrier to data management problems.

In this era where sequencing has never been so accessible, there is an immense need to publish research in a systematic and transparent way. And so how do we respect patient data and privacy regulations and at the same time integrate all literature available to allow for fast and reproducible variant interpretation? Hopefully this episode today answered these questions. And as we have seen, the main bottleneck is still people.

Behind every genetic disease diagnosis, there are data managers, curators, genome analysts, machine learning developers, doctors, scientists that are developing variant effect map or establishing gene disease relationships, and of course, the patients that make this possible. The whole world of medicine is fueled by an enormous pipeline of knowledge discovery, and it's not possible to dream of a world of precision medicine without a framework to integrate all of this knowledge.

Hopefully you're convinced that MAVE integration is a critical step for clinical variant interpretation. And this is why our podcast will continue to advocate for every single aspect that will eventually lead to an atlas of variant effect. But until then, now's the time for the rapid fire questions.

Moez: Are you ready?

Courtney Thaxton: I think so.

Moez: DNA or RNA?

Courtney Thaxton: DNA.

Heidi Rehm: DNA.

Moez: R or Python?

Courtney Thaxton: I like snakes. Python.

Heidi Rehm: Python, because I like snakes.

Moez: Short read or long read?

Courtney Thaxton: Short read.

Heidi Rehm: Short read.

Moez: Single cell or bulk?

Courtney Thaxton: Bulk.

Heidi Rehm: Single cell.

Moez: Knock in or knock out?

Courtney Thaxton: Knock in.

Heidi Rehm: Knock in.

Moez: Golden Gate or Gibson?

Heidi Rehm: Gibson.

Courtney Thaxton: Are we talking about bridges or guitars?

Moez: Coding or non-coding?

Courtney Thaxton: Coding.

Heidi Rehm: Non-coding.

Moez: *In vitro* or *in vivo*?

Courtney Thaxton: *In vitro*.

Heidi Rehm: *In vivo*.

Moez: Favorite model organism?

Courtney Thaxton: Mouse.

Heidi Rehm: Mouse.

Moez: Favorite scientist?

Courtney Thaxton: I did like Albert Einstein.

Heidi Rehm: Rosalind Franklin.

Moez: Favorite media?

Courtney Thaxton: PBS.

Heidi Rehm: NPR.

Moez: Favorite sequencing technology?

Courtney Thaxton: Whole exome and whole genome sequencing.

Heidi Rehm: Illumina.

Moez: Favorite piece of lab equipment?

Courtney Thaxton: Incubators.

Heidi Rehm: Robotic liquid handlers.

Moez: Favorite science movie/ media?

Heidi Rehm: Good Will hunting.

Courtney Thaxton: Oh, this podcast.

Moez: Something outside the lab that you wish you could multiplex.

Courtney Thaxton: I guess most people would say themselves.

Heidi Rehm: Weeding my garden.

Moez: What is the smartest thing you've ever done in the lab?

Courtney Thaxton: Asking questions and not being afraid to.

Heidi Rehm: Rebuild the gel rigs when I used to work in the wet lab.

Moez: And the last question here, what is the stupidest thing that you've ever done in the lab?

Heidi Rehm: Run a gel in the reverse electronic direction.

Courtney Thaxton: It would be forgetting to turn on a piece of equipment. It actually worked.

Alex Nguyen Ba: To all you listeners, I really hope you enjoyed today's episode, which marks the last of the season. Don't forget to tune in though for the next season of Variants and Us, where we'll discuss many other topics in the field of medical genomics and how MAVEs are playing a key role in the development of new cures.

[outro music]